

Assessment of Self-Reported Practice Regarding Kangaroo Mother Care Among Nurses in Lagos State, Nigeria

AUTHOR(S): OJO, Eunice Abimbola (RN, RM, RNA, BNSc., M.Sc. Soc, M.Sc. Nurs)
ADEMUYIWA, Iyabo Yewande (RN, RM, RNE, B.Sc., M.Sc. Ph.D)
OPE-BABADELE, Oluwatosin O. (RN, RM, BNSc., M.Sc.)
And
PERETOMODE, Evans O. (RN, RM, RPHN, BNSc.)

Abstract

In Nigeria, there is a high prevalence of preterm and low birth weight infants, with 16% of new-borns being low birth weight and 12% born preterm. This could be as a result of their practice regarding mother care. Hence, this research study assessed self-reported practice regarding kangaroo mother care among nurses in Lagos State, Nigeria. The study specifically investigated nurses' self-reported practices of kangaroo mother care; and determined factors influencing nurses' practice of kangaroo mother care. The research design utilised was a descriptive survey design. The population for this study comprised nurses working at the neonatal intensive care units (NICUs) of the selected health facilities in Lagos State. Convenient sampling technique was used to select the 130 nurses working at the neonatal intensive care units (NICUs) of the selected health facilities. The survey instrument was the Kangaroo Care Questionnaire (KCQ) which was modified and adapted for local language use. The instrument was presented to experts of Tests and Measurement, and Nursing Education to ascertain the face and content validity of the instrument and confirm relevance to the area of research. The number of copies of questionnaire distributed were 130 but 125 were returned giving a response rate of 96.2%. The data collected were analysed using SPSS version 20 via descriptive statistics. The findings of the study revealed that the majority of the respondents 73(58.4%) never practiced KMC, 33(26.4%) reported sometimes practicing KMC and 19(15.2%) indicated they regularly practice KMC. The practice of KMC is limited due to factors such as

CJAR

Accepted 25 November 2020

Published 30 November 2020

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4319217

fear of impending technological aspects of neonatal care, inadequate staffing and facilities and family reluctance to engage in this practice. It was recommended among others that Government, through the Ministry of Health, should address the challenge of inadequate human resources and facilities which impede KMC implementation.

Keywords: Nurse, Self-Reported Practice, Kangaroo Mother Care (KMC),

About Author

Author(s): OJO, Eunice Abimbola (RN, RM, RNA, BNSc., M.Sc. Soc, M.Sc. Nurs)
School of Nursing Science,
Babcock University, Ilishan-Remo, Ogun State, Nigeria.

ADEMUYIWA, Iyabo Yewande (RN, RM, RNE, B.Sc., M.Sc. Ph.D)
Department of Nursing Science,
Faculty of Clinical Sciences,
University of Lagos, Lagos, Nigeria.

OPE-BABADELE, Oluwatosin O. (RN, RM, BNSc., M.Sc.)
School of Nursing Science,
Babcock University, Ilishan-Remo, Ogun State, Nigeria.

And

PERETOMODE, Evans O. (RN, RM, RPHN, BNSc.)
Department of Nursing Science,
University of PortHarcourt, PortHarcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria.

Introduction

The World Health Organisation (WHO) (2016) reported that every year more than 20 million infants are born weighing less than 2500g, with over 96% of these born in lower-middle-income countries. According to Wagura, Wasunna, Laving, Wamalwa, and Ng'ang'a (2018), infants of African origin have a 12 times greater risk of neonatal death due to complications of preterm birth when compared to their counterparts in the high income and well-resourced countries.

Many deaths due to preterm birth are preventable (Chan, Valsangkar, Kajeepeta, Boundy & Wall, 2016). According to WHO (2016), appropriate care of infants with low birth weight, such as feeding, temperature maintenance, hygienic cord and skincare, and early detection and treatment of infections and complications can substantially reduce mortality in both high income and low- and middle-income countries. WHO (2016) advocates that to reduce neonatal and infant mortality rates, efforts should be geared towards improving the care for the mother during pregnancy and childbirth and in particular of LBW infants; therefore, the recommended three areas of focus are midwife-led continuity of care, specific clinical interventions and Kangaroo Mother Care.

Kangaroo Mother Care (KMC), also known as skin-to-skin contact (SSC), has had varied definitions in the literature and lacks an accepted standardized definition (Chan et al., 2016). Nyqvist et al. (2010), defined KMC as 'a standardized, protocol-based care system for preterm and/or LBW infants, based on skin-to-skin contact between the preterm baby and the mother'. Moore, Bergman, Anderson and Medley (2016) suggested that skin-to-skin contact ideally begins at birth and involves placing the dried, naked baby prone on the mother's bare chest, often covered with a warm blanket. A systematic review of the definition of KMC by Chan et al., (2016) reported that skin to skin contact is the core component of KMC, whereas components such as breastfeeding, early discharge, and follow-up care are context-specific.

There are four components of KMC: early, continuous, and prolonged skin-to-skin contact between infant and caregiver, exclusive breastfeeding, early discharge from hospital, and adequate support for caregiver and infant at home. KMC has long been prescribed and utilized as a natural method of thermoregulation for premature and low birth weight neonates in underdeveloped, developing and developed countries (Charpak et al., 2017). According to Smith, Bergelson, Constantian, Valsangkar and Chan (2017), KMC is one of the evidence-based life-saving interventions that can help reduce neonatal deaths. KMC has been shown to improve the survival rate of low birth weight (LBW) newborns, especially in low and middle-income countries. It has been described as a simple procedure, in which the role of the Kangaroo healthcare provider is to teach, coach, offer expert counselling and closely monitor the mother-infant dyad (Bergh, Charpak, Ezeonodo, Udani, & Van Rooyen, 2012).

Factors influencing the practice of KMC by nurses are barriers or enablers reported to influence the practice. These can be individual, facility/institutional or recipient factors. Individual factors are factors concerning the nurses e.g. the belief that KMC adds to the nurses' workload, reluctance to teach mothers, fear of arterial/venous line dislodgement, lack of knowledge and experience about KMC. Facility/Institutional factors are inadequate facility/bed space, lack of institutional policy on KMC and staff shortage. Recipient factors are family reluctance to accept or practice KMC, the belief of the parents that using an incubator is more beneficial, sick mother/carer and patient discouragement.

KMC has benefits for both mother and infant with a positive outcome in infants of mothers who practiced KMC when compared to newborns who do not have such care. Conde-Agudelo and Diaz-Rossello (2016), in a Cochrane systematic review, provided evidence that supports the use of KMC as an alternative to conventional neonatal care for low birth weight

infants, especially in resource-limited settings. Newborns cared for with this approach have been reported to demonstrate physiological, behavioural, breastfeeding, psychological and neurobehavioural benefits (Conde-Agudelo, Belizán & Diaz-Rossello, 2011; Moore, Bergman, Anderson & Medley, 2016) and reduced pain experience in preterm infants (Gao et al., 2015).

Vittner, Cong, Ludington-Hoe and McGrath (2017) conducted a survey of skin-to-skin contact with perinatal nurses in Connecticut, USA, aimed at exploring perinatal nurses' knowledge, attitudes and practices of KMC. The participants strongly agreed that it was the nurses' responsibility to advocate for KMC. Significant differences ($p < 0.01$) were reported in the provision of KMC with eligible infants between nurses within and between practice settings, education levels, year experience and age differences. Education levels significantly influenced attitudes and implementation of KMC. Perinatal nurses' responses about how difficult it is to initiate KMC changes were affected by the number of nursing practice years ($p < 0.04$). Perinatal nurses strongly believe in KMC practices, yet additional training regarding KMC implementation is needed. Education levels, primary practice settings and years of practice appear to influence nurses' implementation of KMC.

In the Lagos state, few health institutions provide neonatal intensive care services for preterm infants and LBW infants. Hospitals have limited facilities, including incubators (Arukaino, 2017) to meet the growing needs of preterm deliveries. From the researcher's experience in her clinical practice, it has been observed that KMC is not standard care for newborns. The general practice in clinical settings in Lagos State is for infants to be separated from their mothers and cared for in an incubator in the neonatal intensive care units (NICUs). Mothers are encouraged to express breast milk for their infants.

In view of the above, the study assessed self-reported practice regarding kangaroo mother care in Lagos State, Nigeria. The study specifically:

- i. investigated nurses' self-reported practices of kangaroo mother care; and
- ii. determined factors influencing nurses' practice of kangaroo mother care

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. What are nurses' self-reported practices of kangaroo mother care in Lagos State, Nigeria?
2. What are the factors influencing nurses' practice of kangaroo mother care in Lagos State, Nigeria?

Methodology

The research design utilised was a descriptive survey design. The population for this study comprised nurses working at the neonatal intensive care units (NICUs) of the selected health facilities in Lagos State. From the facility at the time of the study, the total population of the nurses was 166 (table 1).

Table 1: Population of respondents per facility

Hospital	Number of nurses in NICU
Lagos University Teaching Hospital	42
Lagos State University Teaching Hospital	36
Gbagada General Hospital	48
Massey Street Children's Hospital	40
Total	166

The sample for this study was derived by using the Taro Yamane formula (Ihudiebube-Splendor, Odikpo, Ogwu, Chinweuba & Osuala, 2019) for sample size determination for a known population below 1000 as shown:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where n = sample size, N = population size, and e = level of precision (0.05)

$$n = \frac{166}{1 + 166(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{166}{1 + 0.415}$$

$$n = \frac{166}{1.415}$$

Therefore, n = 117

Thus, the adjusted sample size is n + 10%n = 130 respondents.

Convenient sampling technique was used to select the 130 nurses working at the neonatal intensive care units (NICUs) of the selected health facilities. The survey instrument was the Kangaroo Care Questionnaire (KCQ) which was modified and adapted for local language use. The KCQ has three sections. Section A sought for the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents while section B consisted of items on self-reported practice regarding KMC and section C consisted of items on factors influencing practice of KMC.

The instrument was presented to experts of Tests and Measurement, and Nursing Education to ascertain the face and content validity of the instrument and confirm relevance to the area of research. The number of copies of questionnaire distributed were 130 but 125 were returned giving a response rate of 96.2%. The data collected were analysed using SPSS version 20 via descriptive statistics.

Results

Research Question 1: What are nurses' self-reported practices of kangaroo mother care in Lagos State, Nigeria?

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics showing Respondents' Practice of KMC (n = 125)

Items	Yes (%)	No (%)
Have you ever:		
Encouraged mothers in the participation of KMC	63(50.4)	62(49.6)
Provided information about KMC to parents	43(34.4)	82(65.6)
Been supervised in the technique of KMC	24(19.2)	101(80.8)
KMC practiced regularly in your ward	48(38.4)	77(61.6)
Persuade mothers with preterm/low birth weight babies to practice KMC	67(53.6)	58(46.4)
Insist mothers practise KMC if they do not respond to persuasion	56(44.8)	69(55.2)
Always look forward to introducing KMC to a new parent	81(64.8)	44(35.2)
Assisted mothers in the participation of KMC with normal term infants	12(9.6)	
with preterm infants (>1000 g.)	24(19.2)	
with preterm infants (<1000 g.)	10(8.0)	
with preterm ventilated infants	6(4.8)	
never	73(58.4)	
Encouraged fathers in the participation of KMC	44(35.2)	81(64.8)
Assisted fathers in the participation of KMC with normal term infants	16(12.8)	
with preterm infants (>1000 g.)	10(8.0)	
with preterm infants (<1000 g.)	6(4.8)	
with preterm ventilated infants	4(3.2)	
never	89(71.2)	
Extent of practice of KMC		
Always	19(15.2)	
Sometimes	33(26.4)	
Never	73(58.4)	
How enthused are you when assisting mothers to practice KMC?	5(4.0)	
Highly enthused	10(8.0)	
Much enthused	18(14.4)	
Moderately enthused	11(8.8)	
Slightly enthused	8(6.4)	
Not enthused at all	73(58.4)	
Not applicable		

Table 2 shows the respondents' self-reported practice of KMC. The majority 73 (58.4%) never practised it, 33 (26.4%) sometimes practised KMC and 19 (15.2%) indicated that they always practice KMC. The majority 82 (65.6%) never provided information about KMC to parents, 101(80.8%) had never been supervised in the technique while 77 (61.6%) did not practice KMC regularly in their units. Eighty-nine (89) (71.2%) had never encouraged fathers to get involved in offering KMC to their infants.

The majority of the respondents 81 (64.8%) desire to introduce KMC to a new parent and 63(50.4%) had encouraged mothers to offer KMC to their newborn infants. Nineteen respondents (15.2%) reported that they always practised KMC, 33 (26.4%) practice sometimes and 73 (58.4%) had never practised KMC.

Research Question 2: What are the factors influencing nurses' practice of kangaroo mother care in Lagos State, Nigeria?

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics showing Factors influencing practice of KMC (n = 125)

Items	Agree (%)	Disagree (%)
Reluctance to practice KMC among nurses	32(25.6)	93(74.4)
Belief that technology (e.g., incubators) is more beneficial to babies than care a parent can provide	44(35.2)	81(64.8)
Family reluctance to initiate and participate in KMC	84(67.2)	41(32.8)
Fear of arterial or venous line dislodgement	88(70.4)	37(29.6)
Nurses' feeling that KMC adds a burden to their workload	37(29.6)	88(70.4)
Parents' discomfort with exposing their chest during KMC	59(47.2)	66(52.8)
Shortage of nursing staff	87(69.6)	38(30.4)
Lack of institutional policy	82(65.6)	43(34.4)
Lack of knowledge of KMC	77(61.6)	48(38.4)
Lack of experience/skill	65(52.0)	60(48.0)
Inadequate facilities/bed space	98(78.4)	27(21.6)

Table 3 above shows the factors influencing practise of KMC. It can be seen that all the items were identified as barriers. Over 70% of respondents indicated that the fear of arterial or venous line dislodgement and inadequate facilities/bed space were major factors influencing their practice of KMC. Other factors indicated by the majority of respondents were family reluctance to initiate and participate in KMC and shortage of nursing staff. However, the majority, 93 (74.4%) did not agree that reluctance to practice KMC was a factor influencing their practice. Eighty-eight 88 (70.4%) disagreed that the feeling that KMC adds a burden to their workload influenced their practice thereof.

Discussion

The findings of the study revealed that over fifty percent (58.4%) of the respondents in the current study had never practiced KMC, 26.4% reported infrequent practice while only 15.2% reported regular KMC practice. This may be due to the knowledge gap and possibly to the lack of support from management, although this could not be determined in this study. Several studies have found the practice of KMC among nurses to be inconsistent (Shah et al., 2018; Deng et al., 2018). Shah et al. (2018) in a study on the knowledge, attitude and practice of KMC among health workers in tertiary health centres in Nepal, reported that only half of the nurses in their study agreed that KMC was practiced regularly in their ward ($p = 0.016$). Deng, et al., (2018), in China, reported that less than half of respondents practiced KMC. In contrast, Solomon and Rosant, (2012) reported that nurses in Cape Town, despite not receiving training, implemented KMC.

The findings in this study have shown that the majority of the respondents did not provide information about KMC to parents (65.6%), KMC was not practiced regularly in their wards (61.6%) and they received no supervision in the technique of KMC (80.8%). This may be due to inadequate knowledge and lack of experience together with the lack of policy guidelines and implementation by facility management. In the current study, 50% mothers were encouraged to provide KMC for their infants, but fathers were not. This could be due to cultural beliefs about the female role in Nigeria. This finding concurs with of Al-Shehri and

Binmanee (2019). Mekle, et al. (2019) also found in their study in India that fathers were not encouraged to support the mothers in providing KMC.

This study has found that although most respondents were positive about KMC, there was some reluctance to practice this and concern about the perceived increase in workload. It is possible that, if the right environment and resources are made available, nurses would be more willing to implement KMC. Seidman et al. (2015), in a systematic review on barriers and enablers of KMC, reported that the actual increased workload due to KMC was the main barrier to the adoption of KMC by nurses in LMICs. Other barriers to adoption of KMC by nurses reported in this study were lack of clear guidelines, resources, level of experience, country specific beliefs and practices and logistical issues (Seidman et al., 2015).

In the current study, factors that were reported to influence the practice of KMC included family reluctance to initiate and participate in KMC, fear related to technological life support measure for the infant, shortage of nursing staff, lack of institutional policy to support implementation and lack of experience/skill. It is essential to provide appropriate training (Mekle et al., 2019) and work towards strengthening health facilities for effective KMC implementation (Jamali et al., 2019). Deng et al., (2018) reported that a major barrier to KMC practice was the reluctance of physicians, and nurses to initiate KMC and parental resistance to the practice.

Conclusion

It was concluded that the majority of the respondents 73(58.4%) never practiced KMC, 33(26.4%) reported sometimes practicing KMC and 19(15.2%) indicated they regularly practice KMC.

The practice of KMC is limited due to factors such as fear of impending technological aspects of neonatal care, inadequate staffing and facilities and family reluctance to engage in this practice.

Recommendations

A number of recommendations are made based on the results of this study:

1. Institutional policies that focus on evidence-based interventions such as KMC should be clearly stated and communicated to workers and strict implementation strategies should be leadership-driven.
2. Government, through the Ministry of Health, should address the challenge of inadequate human resources and facilities which impede KMC implementation.
3. The challenge of implementation of KMC, which has been shown to have benefits for mother, infant and the health services, requires further study, especially in Nigeria.

References

- Al-Shehri, H., & Binmanee, A. (2019). Kangaroo mother care practice, knowledge, and perception among NICU nurses in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. *International journal of paediatrics and adolescent medicine*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpam.2019.11.003>
- Arukaino, U. (2017). Incubators scarcity hampers deliveries in public hospitals. The Punch Newspaper. Retrieved from <https://punchng.com/incubators-scarcity-hampers-deliveries-in-public-hospitals/>
- Bergh, A. M., Charpak, N., Enzeonodo, A., Udani, R., & VanRooyen, E. (2012). For the KMC education and training working group. Education and training in the implementation of kangaroo mother care. *S Afr J Child Health.*, 6(2), 38–45. doi: 1.7196/SAJCH.417
- Chan, G. J., Valsangkar, B., Kajeepeeta, S., Boundy, E. O., & Wall, S. (2016). What is kangaroo mother care? Systematic review of the literature. *J Global Health*, 6(1), 1 – 9. doi: [10.7189/jogh.06.010701](https://doi.org/10.7189/jogh.06.010701)
- Charpak, N., Tessier, R., Ruiz, J. G., Hernandez, J. T., Uriza, F., Villegas, J., . . . Maldonado, D. (2017). Twenty-year follow-up of Kangaroo mother care versus traditional care. *Pediatrics*, 139(1). doi: 10.1542/peds.2016-2063.
- Conde-Agudelo, A., & Diaz-Rossello, J. (2016). Kangaroo mother care to reduce morbidity and mortality in low birth weight infants. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* (4), <https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD002771.pub4>
- Conde-Agudelo, A., Belizan, J. M., & Diaz-Rossello, J. (2011). Kangaroo mother care to reduce morbidity and mortality in low birth weight infants. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* (3), CD002771.
- Deng, O., Zhang, Y., Li, Q., Wang, H., & Xu, X. (2018). Factors that have an impact on knowledge, attitude and practice related to kangaroo care: National survey study among neonatal nurses. *Journal of Clinical Nursing*, 27(21-22), 4100 – 4111. doi: 10.1111/jocn.14556
- Gao, H., Xu, G., Gao, H., Dong, R., Fu, H., Wang, D., . . . Zhang, H. (2015). Effect of repeated kangaroo mother care on repeated procedural pain in preterm infants: A randomized controlled trial. *International Journal of Nursing Studies*, 52(7) 1157–1165. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijnurstu.2015.04.006>
- Jamali, Q.Z., Shah, R., Shahid, F., Fatima, A., Khalsa, S., Spacek, J., ... Regmi, P. (2019). Barriers and enablers for practicing kangaroo mother care (KMC) in rural Sindh, Pakistan. *PLoS ONE*, 14(6), 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0213225>
- Mekle, D., Singh, A.K., & Dixit, J. (2019). Kangaroo mother care for low birth weight babies: supportive factors and barriers. *International Journal of Contemporary Pediatrics*, 6(4), 1737-1742. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.18203/2349-3291.ijcp20192786>
- Moore, E. R., Bergman, N., Anderson, G. C. & Medley, N. (2016). Early skin-to-skin contact for mothers and their healthy newborn infants. *Cochrane Systematic Review-Intervention*, 2016(11). <https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD003519.pub4>
- Nyqvist, K. H., Anderson, C. G., Bergman, N., Cattaneo, A., Charpak, N., Davanzo, R.,... Widstrom, A-M. (2010). State of the art and recommendations: Kangaroo mother care: application in a high-tech environment. *Acta Paediatr*, 99, 812-819. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1651-2227.2010.01794.x>
- Seidman, G., Unnikrishnan, S., Kenny, E., Myslinski, S., Cairns-Smith, S., Brian Mulligan., ... Engmann, C. (2015). Barriers and Enablers of Kangaroo Mother Care Practice: A Systematic Review. *Plos one*, 10 (5), 1-20. doi: [10.1371/journal.pone.0125643](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0125643)

- Shah, R., Sainju, N., & Joshi, S. (2018). Knowledge, attitude and practice towards kangaroo mother care. *Journal of Nepal Health Research Council*, 15(37), 275-81. doi: 10.3126/jnhrc.v15i3.18855.
- Smith, E.R., Bergelson, I., Constantian, S., Valsangkar, B., & Chan, G.J. (2017). Barriers and enablers of health system adoption of kangaroo mother care: a systematic review of caregiver perspectives. *BMC Pediatrics*, 17(35), 1-16. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12887-016-0769-5>
- Solomon, N. & Rosant, C. (2012). Knowledge and attitude of nursing staff and mothers towards kangaroo mother care (KMC) in the eastern sub-district of Cape Town. *South African Journal of Clinical Nutrition*, 25(1), 33 - 39. <https://doi.org/10.1080/16070658.2012.11734400>
- Vittner, D., Cong, X., Ludington-Hoe, S., & McGrath, J. (2017). A survey of skin-to-skin contact with perinatal nurses. *Applied Nursing Research*, 33(1), 19-33. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apnr.2016.09.006>
- Wagura, P., Wasunna, A., Laving, A., Wamalwa, D. & Ng'ang'a, P. (2018). Prevalence and factors associated with preterm birth at Kenyatta National Hospital. *BMC Pregnancy and Childbirth*, 18(107), 1-8. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12884-018-1740-2>
- World Health Organization. (2016). WHO recommendations on antenatal care for a positive pregnancy experience. Accessed 4/9/2019 at https://www.who.int/reproductivehealth/publications/maternal_perinatal_health/anc-positive-pregnancy-experience/en/

Cite this article:

Author(s), OJO, Eunice Abimbola (RN, RM, RNA, BNSc., M.Sc. Soc, M.Sc. Nurs), ADEMUYIWA, Iyabo Yewande (RN, RM, RNE, B.Sc., M.Sc. Ph.D), OPE-BABADELE, Oluwatosin O. (RN, RM, BNSc., M.Sc.), And PERETOMODE, Evans O. (RN, RM, RPHN, BNSc.), (2020). "Assessment of Self-Reported Practice Regarding Kangaroo Mother Care Among Nurses in Lagos State, Nigeria". **Name of the Journal:** Commonwealth Journal of Academic Research, (CJAR.EU), P, 12- 21. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4319217> , SPECIAL ISSUE, Issue: 8, Vol.: 1, Article: 1, Month: November, Year: 2020. Retrieved from <https://www.cjar.eu/all-issues/>

Published by

AND

ThoughtWares Consulting & Multi Services International (TWCMSI)

